

The Influence of School Principals' Academic Supervision on Teacher Performance at SMK Negeri 2 Siatas Barita in 2023

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Article History

Received: 12.03.2024
Accepted: 02.04.2024
Published: 27.04.2024

Abstract: *The purpose of this study was to determine the effect of the principal's academic supervision on teacher performance at SMK Negeri 2 Siatas Barita in 2023. The method used in this research is quantitative research method. The population is all teachers at SMK Negeri 2 Siatas Barita with a total of 64 teachers and this research is a population study. Data were collected with a positive closed questionnaire of 46 items. The results of data analysis show that there is an influence of the principal's academic supervision on teacher performance at SMK Negeri 2 Siatas Barita in 2023. 1) Test of analysis requirements: a) positive influence test obtained r_{xy} value = $0.486 > r_{table} (\alpha = 0.05, n = 64) = 0.244$ thus it is known that there is a positive influence between variable X and variable Y. b) significant relationship test obtained $t_{count} = 4.380 > t_{table} (\alpha = 0.05, dk = n-2 = 62) = 2.000$ thus there is a significant relationship between variable X and variable Y. 2) Effect test: a) Regression equation test, obtained regression equation $\hat{Y} = 53.452 + 0.278X$. b) Regression determination coefficient test (r^2) = 23.6%. 3) Hypothesis testing using the F test obtained $F_{count} > F_{table}$, namely $19.188 > 4.00$. Thus H_a is accepted and H_0 is rejected.*

Keywords: *Academic Supervision, Principal, Teacher Performances.*

Cite this article:

Berutu, L., Tobing, L.L., Nababan, M.L., (2024). The Influence of School Principals' Academic Supervision on Teacher Performance at SMK Negeri 2 Siatas Barita in 2023. *ISAR Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences*, 2(4), 29-34.

Introduction

Education is a lifelong activity aimed at assisting and nurturing human personality in accordance with moral values within their social and cultural environment. Education plays a crucial role in preparing human resources with expertise, based on the process of forming attitudes and behaviors of individuals or groups in a conscious and planned manner through continuous teaching stages. Education is a fundamental asset for every nation and country in building the nation to achieve its aspirations and become an advanced society. Therefore, good education outcomes should also reflect high quality and outstanding achievements.

According to the Law of the Republic of Indonesia No. 30 of 2003 on the National Education System, education is a conscious and planned effort to create a learning atmosphere and learning process so that students actively develop their potential to possess religious faith, self-control, good personality, intelligence, noble character, and the skills needed by themselves, society, the nation, and the state. Education can have a positive impact on the development of a nation towards becoming an advanced society. Therefore, good education outcomes should also reflect high quality and outstanding achievements. Education can continuously

change a person's behavior, character, and attitude, thereby forming individuals capable of discerning between good and bad actions. One of the goals of education is to improve the quality of human resources through the learning process in schools.

Teachers are individuals who hold a crucial position in education. They play a highly dominant and essential role in the education of students, often serving as role models for them. Teachers are at the forefront of education as they directly influence, nurture, and develop the interests and talents of students. They are required to possess the fundamental skills necessary as educators, mentors, and instructors, and these abilities reflect their competence. This aligns with the research conducted by Tobing et al. (2023), which states that educators with competence will achieve optimal performance.

Teacher performance in an educational institution represents the tangible work outcomes, both in quality and quantity, achieved by teachers in carrying out their assigned duties and responsibilities. This includes preparing lesson plans, conducting teaching, and evaluating student learning outcomes. Teachers must create lesson plans before executing their teaching tasks in the classroom to work optimally in imparting knowledge to students. The evaluation of student learning outcomes is conducted to follow

up on the teaching process and to identify the strengths and weaknesses within the learning process.

The principal plays a crucial role in improving and enhancing the quality of education and instruction in schools, which are the primary objectives of education. As a leader, the principal must possess the ability to conduct supervision. Academic supervision is the principal's effort to oversee the learning process, focusing on the teacher's role in conducting the teaching and learning process to improve educational quality and achieve educational goals. The improvement of teaching and learning quality is guided by the teacher's duties in the teaching process. The principal contributes to enhancing teacher performance by providing support to develop their knowledge, increase their teaching capacity, and improve their performance, thereby enabling teachers to better understand the learning process. The principal controls the management of the educational institution and acts as a supervisor responsible for monitoring teacher performance in the school. The principal is accountable for conducting academic supervision of the teachers and providing guidance to help improve their teaching performance.

Academic supervision by the school principal can be evaluated based on their ability to see themselves as an academic supervisor. Therefore, in the process of academic supervision, the principal requires support from the government. The principal must perform their duties as a supervisor by providing feedback and guidance to teachers in conducting the learning process and developing their professionalism, rather than aiming for perfection and assessing teachers. The goal of academic supervision is to enhance the quality of the learning process by offering feedback, guiding, and improving the quality of teachers, thereby enhancing their performance.

According to Suhayati, inadequate academic supervision by the principal can disrupt teacher performance due to the lack of comprehensive academic supervision, as principals fail to fulfill all their duties and responsibilities. The teaching conducted by teachers must be continuously and long-term monitored and guided. Given the critical role of teachers in the success of education, principals, as supervisors, must strive to enhance the quality of teaching performed by teachers to achieve educational goals. Principals must be capable of providing academic supervision to teachers so that teaching issues faced by teachers can be resolved through continuous guidance.

Academic supervision conducted by the principal significantly affects a teacher's performance in carrying out their teaching duties at school. Through supervision by the principal, teachers can communicate any issues or obstacles they encounter in their role. Teachers facing challenges in the learning process should be mentored and guided so that these issues can be resolved. This approach will have a positive impact on teachers, enabling them to improve their performance.

Based on the observations and interviews conducted by the researcher at SMK Negeri 2 Siatas Barita, several issues related to teacher performance were identified. These issues include teachers not adhering to the scheduled teaching times set by the school and some teachers leaving the classroom during the learning process, resulting in less effective teaching. Another problem is that some teachers are unable to manage disruptive students, leading to a

disturbed learning environment. The use of monotonous teaching media that does not utilize audiovisual aids further hampers the learning process. In the 4.0 era, it is essential for teachers to employ more advanced teaching media. Therefore, continuous follow-up efforts are needed to achieve optimal performance, making academic supervision by the principal essential for teachers.

Based on the background issues identified above, the author is motivated to choose the title *The Influence of School Principals' Academic Supervision on Teacher Performance at SMK Negeri 2 Siatas Barita in 2023*.

Methods

This study is a means of revealing the truth about what is considered scientific knowledge. By conducting this research, the researcher can observe, examine, and analyze an object to discover new insights and attain truth. This study utilizes a quantitative research method based on the type of data involved. Research methods, in essence, are scientific approaches to obtaining data for specific purposes and uses (Sugiyono, 2017). According to Arikunto (2017), quantitative research often relies on numerical data, from data collection and interpretation to the analysis of results.

In alignment with the title of this research, *'The Influence of School Principals' Supervision on Teacher Performance at SMK Negeri 2 Siatas Barita in 2023'*, the study is conducted at SMK Negeri 2 Siatas Barita. The choice of this location is based on the existing issues related to teacher performance. Therefore, the researcher aims to determine the extent to which academic supervision by the principal affects teacher performance at SMK Negeri 2 Siatas Barita.

Population refers to the entire set of research objects that serve as the data source for the researcher. The determination of the population is crucial for the implementation of the research. By defining the population, the researcher aims to ensure the study is conducted effectively. According to Sugiyono (2017), the population is the generalization area consisting of objects/subjects with specific qualities and characteristics defined by the researcher for study and subsequent conclusion. In this study, the population consists of all teachers at SMK Negeri 2 Siatas Barita, totaling 64 teachers. According to Arikunto (2017), if the number of subjects is fewer than 100, it is preferable to include the entire population, making the study a population research. Given that the population is less than 100, this research includes the entire population as the sample, thus classifying the study as a population research.

Result And Discussion

This study employs two related variables: School Principal's Academic Supervision as variable X and Teacher Performance as variable Y. In this research, the author uses a closed questionnaire instrument, consisting of four choices: a, b, c, and d. The questionnaire is designed to align with the research objectives. The research instrument is developed in accordance with the research object, based on theoretical foundations, and adjusted to the indicators in the questionnaire grid as follows:

Table 1

No	Variable	Indicator	No Item
1	Principal Academic Supervision (Variable X)	Planning academic supervision	1,2, and 3
		Carry out academic supervision using approaches and techniques	4,5,6,7,8,9,10, 11,12,13,14, and 15,
		Follow up on the results of academic supervision	16,17,18,19,20, 21,22, and 23,
2	Teacher Performance (Variable Y)	Planning learning	24,25,26,27,28, 29,30,31, and 32,
		Implementing quality learning and assessing	33,34,35,36,37, 38,39,40,41,42, and 43,
		Evaluating learning	44,45 and 46
	Amount		46

To determine the relationship between variable X (school principal's academic supervision) and variable Y (teacher performance) at SMK Negeri 2 Siatas Barita in 2023, the Pearson Product Moment Correlation formula is used, as stated by Arikunto (2017) as follows:

$$r_{xy} = \frac{N \sum xy - (\sum X)(\sum Y)}{(\sqrt{\sum X^2 - (\sum X)^2})(\sqrt{\sum Y^2 - (\sum Y)^2})}$$

The following are the results of the correlation test after being calculated using the SPSS 25 application

Table 2: Correlation Test Results for Variable X to Y

		Variabel_X	Variabel_Y
Variabel_X	Pearson Correlation	1	,486**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		,000
	N	64	64
Variabel_Y	Pearson Correlation	,486**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	,000	
	N	64	64

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Based on the calculation of (r_{xy}) using the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation formula, the value obtained is $(r_{xy} = 0.486)$. This $(r_{\text{calculated}})$ value is compared with the (r_{table}) value $(\alpha = 0.05)$; CI = 95%; $(n = 64)$, which is 0.244. Since $(r_{\text{calculated}} > r_{\text{table}})$ $(0.486 > 0.244)$, there is a positive relationship between variable X and variable Y, indicating a positive influence of the school principal's academic supervision on teacher performance at SMK Negeri 2 Siatas Barita in 2023.

Significant Relationship Test (t test)

To test the significance of the relationship, i.e., whether the identified relationship applies to the entire population, it is necessary to test its significance (Sugiyono, 2017). The formula for testing the significance of the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation is shown as follows:

$$t = \frac{r\sqrt{n-2}}{\sqrt{1-r^2}}$$

The following are the results of the significant relationship test using the SPSS application

Table 3

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	53,452	4,713		11,342	,000
Variabel_X	,278	,064	,486	4,380	,000

a. Dependent Variable: Variabel_Y

A calculated ttt-value of 4.380 was obtained. This ttt-value is then compared with the critical ttt-value for $\alpha=0.05$ for a two-tailed test and degrees of freedom $df=n-2=64-2=62$, yielding $t_{table}=2.000$. Since $t_{calculated} > t_{table}$ (4.380 > 2.000), it can be concluded that there is a significant influence between variable X and variable Y, indicating a significant effect of the school principal's academic supervision on teacher performance at SMK Negeri 2 Siatas Barita in 2023.

Regression Analysis

The regression equation can be used to predict the value of the dependent variable based on changes in the independent variable (Sugiyono, 2017). Regression analysis can be conducted using the following formula:

$$\hat{Y} = a + bX$$

Dimana:

\hat{Y} = Predicted value

a = constant

b = Regression coefficient

X = Variable X value

Table 4: Regression Analysis Results

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	53,452	4,713		11,342	,000
Variabel_X	,278	,064	,486	4,380	,000

a. Dependent Variable: Variabel_Y

Thus, the values of aaa and bbb are obtained as follows:

To determine the regression equation of Y on X, the following formula is used:

$$\hat{Y} = a + bX$$

By entering the values obtained from the calculations above, a simple regression equation is obtained, namely:

$$\hat{Y} = 53,452 + 0,278 X$$

This regression equation indicates that, with a constant value of 53.452, for every unit increase in variable X (school principal's academic supervision), there will be an increase in variable Y (teacher performance) by 0.278 from the value of the school principal's academic supervision (variable X).

Coefficient of Determination Test (r^2)

The following are the results of the coefficient of determination test

Table 5: Coefficient of Determination Test Results

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	,486^a	,236	,224	5,85629

a. Predictors: (Constant), Variabel_X

b. Dependent Variable: Variabel_Y

Correlation analysis can be further extended by calculating the coefficient of determination, by squaring the obtained coefficient (Sugiyono, 2017). Based on this approach, the coefficient of determination (r^2) can be calculated using the following formula:

$$r^2 = (r_{xy})^2$$

$$r^2 = (0,486)^2$$

$$r^2 = 0,236$$

Furthermore, according to Sugiyono, 'the coefficient of determination test can be used to calculate the percentage of the effectiveness of X on Y by multiplying the r^2 value by 100% ($r^2 \times 100\%$). From the calculation, an r^2 value of 0.236 was obtained. This value indicates that the percentage influence of the school principal's academic supervision on teacher performance at SMK Negeri 2 Siatas Barita in 2023 is: ($r^2 \times 100\% = 0.236 \times 100\% = 23.6\%$).

F Value Testing

The following are the results of the Variance Analysis calculation (ANOVA)

Table 6

ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	658,074	1	658,074	19,188	,000^b
Residual	2126,363	62	34,296		
Total	2784,437	63			

a. Dependent Variable: Variable_Y

b. Predictors: (Constant), Variable_X

From the calculation table, an $F_{\text{calculated}}$ value of 19.188 is obtained. When compared with the F_{table} value for $\alpha = 0.05$, with degrees of freedom for the numerator k (independent variables) = 1 and degrees of freedom for the denominator $n - k = 64 - 1 = 63$, which is 4.00, we find that $F_{\text{calculated}} > F_{\text{table}}$ ($19.188 > 4.00$). Based on this value, the hypothesis of the research can be determined as follows:

$H_0: \beta = 0$ is rejected, and $H_a: \beta \neq 0$ is accepted if $F_{\text{calculated}} \geq F_{\text{table}}$.

Thus, H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted, indicating a positive and significant effect of the school principal's academic supervision on teacher performance at SMK Negeri 2 Siatas Barita in 2023.

Based on the research conducted with teachers at SMK Negeri 2 Siatas Barita in 2023, it was found that the school principal's academic supervision has an impact on teacher performance at SMK Negeri 2 Siatas Barita in 2023. The competencies in academic supervision that a principal must possess are: 1) Planning academic supervision to enhance teacher professionalism, 2) Implementing academic supervision with appropriate approaches

and techniques, and 3) Following up on the results of academic supervision to improve teacher professionalism. Therefore, it is anticipated that the implementation of academic supervision by the principal will improve teacher performance at SMK Negeri 2 Siatas Barita in 2023, as evidenced by the effective completion of teacher tasks, including planning lessons, delivering high-quality instruction, and evaluating learning outcomes .

Conclusion

From the research results, it is known that from the hypothesis test, the value $F_{\text{count}} > F_{\text{table}}$ is obtained, namely $19,188 > 4,00$. Thus, the research hypothesis is accepted. It can be concluded that there is a positive and significant influence of the school principal's academic supervision on teacher performance at SMK Negeri 2 Siatas Barita in 2023, amounting to 23.6%. The more frequently academic supervision is conducted by the school principal, the greater the improvement in teacher performance at SMK Negeri 2 Siatas Barita in 2023.

Based on the findings of this research, it is expected that the school principal and teachers will maintain and even further enhance their performance. For future researchers interested in

studying teacher performance, it is recommended to explore other variables that may influence teacher performance. Additionally, those who wish to investigate other impacts of the school principal's academic supervision should consider linking it to other variables, as it is possible that it affects various aspects related to the principal's academic supervision.

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